

```
1 *****
2 *****
3 *
4 *       File 3. Analysis Code (for the IDEaL Study cost and cost
5 *       effectiveness analysis)
6 *       Bruce A. Larson
7 *       (IDEaL activity costs through 4 week clinic follow up
8 *       visit)
9 *
10 *
11 *
12 *****
13 *****
14
15 /* use this dataset (IDEaL service quantities data set, File 3 in
16 the OpenBU
17 repository
18 Larson original file name: use
19 "/...../ideal_intervention_costing_28Sept2023 n 549 costing.dta"
20
21 The first step is to pull in the final unit cost estimates from
22 IDEaL unit cost
23 Excel file. The latest version used for this analysis is:
24
25 In the OpenBU repository, the file name is: File 1 – IDEaL Cost
26 Methods and Results Tables.xlsx
```

Methods and Results Tables.xlsx

22

23 */

24

25 scalar cy1 = 12.04

26 scalar cy2 = 0.65

27 scalar cy3 = 9.09

28 scalar cy4 = 0.49

29 scalar cy5 = 2.95

30 scalar cy6 = 5.72

31 scalar cy7 = 4.96

32 scalar cy8 = 0.34

33

34 scalar cz1 = 33.88

35 scalar cz2 = 0.92

36 scalar cz3 = 30.74

37 scalar cz4 = 0.75

38 scalar cz5 = 8.99

39 scalar cz6 = 2.40

40 scalar cz7 = 6.31

41 scalar cz8 = 2.40

42 scalar cz9 = 0.55

43

44 scalar cm1 = 16.66

45 scalar cm2 = 1.59

46 scalar cm3 = 13.39

47 scalar cm4 = 1.28

48 scalar cm5 = 7.69

49 scalar cm6 = 0.42

50 scalar cm7 = 8.01

51 scalar cm8 = 4.96

52

53

54 * Define total costs for patient supporter services all study arms

```
54 * Define total costs for patient supporter services all study arms
55
56
57 gen cost_PS = y_us_h * cy1 + ///
58 y_us_f * cy2 + ///
59 y_h * cy3 + ///
60 y_f * cy4 + ///
61 y_ct * cy5 + ///
62 y_fi * cy6 + ///
63 y_4week * cy7 + ///
64 y_pc * cy8
65
66
67 * Define total cost for nurse services (arm 2 and arm 3)
68
69
70 gen cost_Nurse = z_us_h * cz1 + ///
71 z_us_f * cz2 + ///
72 z_h * cz3 + ///
73 z_f * cz4 + ///
74 z_ct * cz5 + ///
75 z_it * cz6 + ///
76 z_4week_clinic * cz7 + ///
77 z_4week_home * cz8 + ///
78 z_pc * cz9
79
80 * Define total cost for mentor services (arm 3)
81
82 gen cost_Mentor = m_us_h * cm1 + ///
```

```
82 gen cost_Mentor = m_us_h * cm1 + ///
83 m_us_f * cm2 + ///
84 m_h * cm3 + ///
85 m_f * cm4 + ///
86 m_ct * cm5 + ///
87 m_pc * cm6 + ///
88 m_fi * cm7 + ///
89 m_4week * cm8
90
91
92
93 * Define total costs per patient
94
95
96 gen cost_IDEaL = cost_PS + cost_Nurse + cost_Mentor
97
98
99
100 * Results for Table 1 and basic effectiveness information within
    Table 8
101
102 * Now just summarize data
103
104
105 tab arm po_success
106
107 table arm initiated_90days
108
109 table arm po_success if initiated_90days == 1
110
111
112 tabstat po_success initiated_90days, by(arm) stat(n mean) col(stat)
    long format(%9.3f) varwidth(15) nototal
```

```
        long format(%9.3f) varwidth(15) nototal
113
114 tabstat po_success if initiated_90days == 1, by(arm) stat(n mean)
    col(stat) long format(%9.3f) varwidth(15) nototal
115
116
117 * Now effectiveness
118
119
120 * Are outcomes different across study arms
121
122
123 reg po_success i.arm, robust
124
125 test 2.arm = 3.arm
126
127
128
129
130
131 * Results for Table 2
132
133 tabstat y_us_h y_us_f y_h y_f y_ct y_fi y_4week y_pc ///
134         z_us_h z_us_f z_h z_f z_ct z_it z_4week_clinic z_4week_home
    z_pc ///
135         m_us_h m_us_f m_h m_f m_ct m_pc m_fi m_4week , ///
136         by(arm) stat(mean median max) col(stat) long format(%9.3f
    ) varwidth(15) nototal
137
138 * Results for Table 6 -- total sample
139
140
```

```
140
141 tabstat cost_PS cost_Nurse cost_Mentor cost_IDEaL, ///
142         by(arm) stat(mean semean) col(stat) long format(%9.3f)
143         varwidth(15) nototal
144
145 * mean cost differences by arm
146
147
148 reg cost_IDEaL i.arm, robust
149
150 * two ways to test if Arm 3 cost less than Arm 2
151
152 test 2.arm = 3.arm
153
154 * also confirm Arm 3 costs less than arm 2
155
156 reg cost_IDEaL i.arm if arm >1, robust
157
158
159 * Results for Table 6 -- subset achieved primary outcome
160     (po_success == 1)
161
162 tabstat cost_PS cost_Nurse cost_Mentor cost_IDEaL if po_success ==
163     1, ///
164         by(arm) stat(mean semean) col(stat) long format(%9.3f)
165         varwidth(15) nototal
166
167 reg cost_IDEaL i.arm if po_success == 1, robust
168
169 reg cost_IDEaL i.arm if po_success == 1 & arm >1, robust
```

```
168 reg cost_IDEaL i.arm if po_success == 1 & arm >1, robust
169
170 * also confirms Arm 3 less than arm 2 for this subset
171
172
173 * Results for Table 6 -- subset did not achieve primary outcome
    (po_success == 1)
174
175
176 tabstat cost_PS cost_Nurse cost_Mentor cost_IDEaL if po_success ==
    0, ///
177     by(arm) stat(mean semean) col(stat) long format(%9.3f)
    varwidth(15) nototal
178
179
180 reg cost_IDEaL i.arm if po_success == 0, robust
181
182 reg cost_IDEaL i.arm if po_success == 0 & arm >1, robust
183
184 * Arm 3 less than arm 2 for this subset but not at 5% level.
185
186
187
188 * Create a density plot by arm
189
190 * Create a separate density plot for each arm
191 twoway (kdensity cost_IDEaL if arm == 1, graphregion(color(white))
    color(blue)) ///
192     (kdensity cost_IDEaL if arm == 2, color(red)) ///
193     (kdensity cost_IDEaL if arm == 3, color(green)), ///
```